

3rd International Conference on Information Technology Convergence Services & AI (ITCAI 2026)

July 28 ~ 29, 2026, Virtual Conference

<https://itcai2026.org/index>

Scope

3rd International Conference on Information Technology Convergence Services & AI (ITCAI 2026) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and new research results in all areas of Information Technology Convergence Services & AI. The Conference focuses on all technical and practical aspects of ITC & AI. The goal of this conference is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on understanding Information Technology Convergence and services, AI, and establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to:

Topics of interest

- AI in IT Convergence & Services
- Business and Information Systems
- Cloud computing, Big data, Internet of Things (IOT) Convergence
- Convergence in Information Technology Security, Trust, Privacy
- Convergence of AI & Computational Intelligence
- Convergence of AI and Bioinformatics
- Cyber-physical systems, Social media analytics and Convergence
- Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery
- Digital Convergence, Electronic Commerce, Business and Management
- Grid and Cloud Computing
- Hardware and Software Design
- Health and Medical Informatics
- Hybrid Information Technology
- Intelligent Communications and Networks
- Intelligent Robotics and Autonomous Agents
- IT-based Convergence Technology and Service
- Machine Learning Convergence
- Multimedia & Education Convergence
- New trends in Convergence
- Smart Card and RFID Technologies
- Social , Business Aspects of Convergence IT
- Next-generation Internet, Blockchains and Services
- Soft Computing and Intelligent Systems
- Ubiquitous Computing and Embedded System

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **May 24, 2026**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the

conference will be published by [International Journal on Cybernetics & Informatics \(IJCI\)](#) (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **ITCAI 2026**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issue of the following journals

- [International Journal of Information Technology Convergence and Services \(IJITCS\)](#)
- [Advanced Computational Intelligence: An International Journal \(ACII\)](#)
- [Advanced Computing: An International Journal \(ACIJ\)](#)
- [International Journal of Computer Science, Engineering and Applications \(IJCSSEA\)](#)

Important Dates

3rd Batch : Submissions after May 11

- **Submission Deadline : May 24, 2026**
- Authors Notification : June 27, 2026
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : July 04, 2026

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : itcai@itcai2026.org or itcaiconf@yahoo.com